

EFFECT OF TOXIC RELEASE ON CHITTAGONG INDUSTRIAL AREA

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ABSTRACT

This paper studied the impact of accidental toxic release in chemical process industry on the surrounding community. The area of interest here is Chittagong industrial zone. The consequences due to toxic release were modeled by risk assessment software ALOHA and used to establish industrial hazard map for the study area. The paper presents the case study of catastrophic ammonia release, which occurred on August 22, 2016 in a Di-Ammonium phosphate plant (DAPFCL) in Chittagong, Bangladesh. It also analyses worst case scenario for fictitious release of ammonia from twenty thousand metric ton ammonia tank of Karnaphuli Fertilizer Company Limited (KAFCO).

KEYWORDS: Industrial hazards, Toxic release, Risk zone, Societal risk

1 INTRODUCTION

Chemical process industries often involve reactors, conduits and storage vessels in which hazardous substances are stored or processed at elevated temperatures and/or pressures. Accidents in such units caused either by equipment malfunctions, material failure (such as crack in the storage vessels), operational error, (Such as raising the pressure temperature, flow rate beyond critical limits), or external perturbation (such as damage caused by a projectile) can have serious - often catastrophic consequences [1]. The most gruesome example of such an accident is the Bhopal Tragedy of 1984 which killed or maimed over 20,000 persons [1, 2] but there have been numerous other accidents i.e. Flixborough—1974, Basel-1986, Antwerp1987, Pasadena-1989, etc. [1] in which the death toll would have been as high as in Bhopal if the areas where the accidents took place were not less densely populated. Furthermore, it is common to find ‘industrial areas’ or ‘industrial complexes’ where groups of industries are situated in close proximity to one another. The growth in the number of such industrial areas and in the number of industries contained in each of the areas gives rise to increasing probabilities of ‘chain of accidents’ or cascading/domino effects wherein an accident in one industry may cause another accident in a neighboring industry which in turn may trigger another accident and so on [1, 3]. Along with the rapid growth of industrialization and population the potential hazard and risk posed by probable accidents also continues to rise. This is particularly so in the developing country like Bangladesh where population density is very high and industrial areas which are surrounded by dense clusters of neighborhood.

The recent incident of ammonia release (22 August, 2016) due to failure of ammonia day tank in DAPFCL in Chittagong raised serious concerns about the probability of such release and their impact on the surrounding population and environment. It was reported that the day tank capacity of which is five hundred metric ton was exploded and completely rift from its base and landed about 35 ft. away from its base. A huge gas cloud was formed and dispersed into the air. The toxic ammonia gas spread over several kilometers and wind carried away the gas to the other bank of the Karnaphuli river leaving nearly 250 people fell sick inhaling the toxic ammonia gas. Fifty two of them were required hospitalization during the same night [4]. In this study an attempt is made to map the industrial zone of Chittagong, identify the probable sources of toxic release, analyze the consequence of such release and prepare a respective hazard map of the area. The real incident of ammonia release in DAPFCL and a fictitious case of ammonia release in KAFCO storage tank are presented as case studies. The KAFCO plant is a fully integrated complex. It lies on 100.03 acres of land, located in Rangadia, Karnaphuli,

Chittagong just alongside the Karnaphuli river. It has a production capacity of one thousand and five hundred metric ton ammonia per day and a total storage capacity of twenty thousand metric ton ammonia.

Various plausible accident scenario can be generated based on chemical properties, operating conditions, and details of the process/storage units. Most common accident scenarios are catastrophic failure due to overpressure and leaking of storage tank [1]. Worst case scenario can be visualized when the largest quantity of substance on site is released within 10 minutes. In this case, liquid is considered to be released at ground level at highest daily maximum temperature. Also, wind speed and stability class are considered to be 1.5 m/s and ‘F’ respectively [5]. Speaking of catastrophic failure, there are many potential causes that lead to it, e.g. faulty tank, internal corrosion, external corrosion, flow interruption, failure of control valve, failure of relief valve, increase of temperature/pressure and/or human error [4]. This particular study deals with estimating the total affected area with certain concentration which helps to identify potential emergency scenarios and develop a proper emergency plan. Also, it has a potential to be used to develop risk-informed land use planning strategy.

2 METHODOLOGY

At first a study area was selected and GIS boundary layer for the area was created in ArcGIS software. Next, industrial mapping was carried out. For consequence analysis we have used ALOHA. Finally threat zone from ALOHA was overlaid on the GIS map to produce industrial hazard map. Research methodology is outlined in figure 1.

Figure 1: Research Methodology

2.1 Selection of Study Area

The study was carried out in Chittagong district. Chittagong has the second largest city and main sea port of Bangladesh situated on the banks of the Karnafuli River. The city lies 22° 14' North to 22° 24'30'' north latitude and 91° 46' east to 92° 14' east longitude and extend north bank of the Karnafuli River to west bank of the Halda River. The city, under the jurisdiction of City Corporation, has a

population of about 2.5 million and is constantly growing (CDA, 2014). Chittagong city has a unique landscape. The river Karnafuli garlands it in the east and the south. The Bay of Bengal embraces it from the west. Beautiful and lush green hills adorn the city in the north [6]. Figure 2 shows the location of Chittagong district. The red rectangular area shows the area under Chittagong City Corporation.

Figure 2: Location of study area

2.2 Generation of Vector GIS Boundary Layer

Latest high resolution satellite imagery provided by Google Earth has been used to create the base map of our study area. Vector GIS Boundary Layer of Chittagong district has been prepared in the ArcGIS software.

2.2.1 Industrial Mapping

Forty large industries and some other process industries are selected for this study. Locational information is taken from Google map and Chittagong District Statistics 2011. Our study covers 21 Steel and Engineering factories, one crude oil and 7 condensate refineries, 9 textiles, 4 fertilizer factories, 4 jute mill, 3 paper mill, 2 glass factories and 2 cement factories. This mapping involves major industries of Chittagong district, but there are numerous industries which have not been mapped due to lack of information.

A comparison with the Bureau of statistics is presented in Figure 3

Figure 3: Comparison of no. of industries covered with that enlisted in Bureau of Statistics.

2.2.2 Thematic Data Layer Generation

Chittagong city has a much diversified land use pattern. Generally, an urban landscape is composed of vegetation and impervious surface which are spectrally too similar to be separated using spectral information of satellite image. Conventionally Pixel-based (PB) and object-based (OB) classification are used in image classification [7-9]. As we are dealing with very low spectral and high spatial resolution data for land use (Industrial Area, Residential Area, local facilities etc.) we have used object-based classification. Although we have studied low spatial resolution satellite image for land cover pattern (Hill forest, Coastal Plane and Vegetation etc.). In this object-based classification, we have created representative polygon layers of our classes in Google Earth. For accurate data collection we have also used Google Street View. We have considered 7 classes including (1) Industrial Area, (2) Residential Area, (3) Water Body, (4) Agriculture, (5) Hill Forest, (6) Coastal Plane and (7) Open Space with Vegetation. Shapefiles for these polygon layers have been created in the ArcGIS 10.5. When all polygon layers are imported in the basemap of the study area, we get the final map for visual interpretation.

2.3 Visual Interpretation

The identification of areas of vulnerability and of specific hazards is of fundamental importance in risk assessment. From the map in figure 4, it is evident that the area under Chittagong City Corporation is the most densely populated (Population density range of 2493-41663 per square kilometer) and also it is highly industrial zone. Moreover, industrial areas and residential areas are in close proximity which implies that for an industrial accident there is a probability of high degree of societal risk. In the map, Blue colored industries are toxic, red refers to flammable and other industries are reactive.

2.3.1 Selection of Facility for Toxic Release

Identification of the hazards is the essential first step of risk assessment. The quality of the assessment depends crucially on the comprehensiveness of the hazard identification [10]. The chemical process industries that are considered here are classified on the basis of the properties of the chemicals they produce or deal with. Chemicals can be harmful in three key ways: flammability, reactivity and toxicity. Flammability represents the harm posed by fires or explosions.

Figure 4: Prepared map for consequence analysis

Reactivity represents the instability of a substance in certain conditions. Toxicity represents the harm posed to human health or the environment. The fertilizer factories deal with toxic chemical like ammonia. Oil refineries are under flammable category. There are some garments, textile and pulp and

paper manufacturing industries under reactive category. Since toxic hazards are the most dominant threat, we will present consequence of toxic release in this paper.

3 CONSEQUENCE ANALYSIS

Evaluation of the consequences and impact associated with the occurrence of postulated accident scenarios in a process is referred to as consequence analysis. This step indicates the understanding of the nature and outcome of an accident and permits the examination and/or prioritization of accident scenario in terms of their potential impact on human and property.

There can be numerous credible scenarios for toxic release from a Chemical Process Industry [11]. We will highlight catastrophic failure of storage tank for different meteorological conditions and loss of total containment. Table 1 presents the selected sources and scenarios of toxic release.

Table 1: List of selected scenarios

Scenario ID	Installation	Containment	Capacity (MT)	Scenario Description
A-DAPFCL	Atmospheric Storage Tank	Anhydrous Ammonia	500	Real case scenario of catastrophic failure
B-KAFCO	Atmospheric Storage Tank	Anhydrous Ammonia	20,000	Worst case scenario

3.1 Scenario A, Case Study 1: DAPFCL Storage Tank Explosion, 22 August, 2016

A large amount of toxic ammonia gas was released around 10 PM, 22 August 2016 due to overpressure explosion of a 500 ton ammonia tank from the Di-ammonium Phosphate Factory Limited known as DAP-1 [4].

Wind rose plot for August 22, 2016 is created for 24 hour time period. Percentage of wind speed is also calculated. The concentric circles represent the various percentage frequencies of time. The innermost circle represents the percentage occurrence of calm (wind speed less than 0.3 m/s). The total length of each arm represents the total percentage frequency of time the wind blows from the direction concerned.

Figure 5: Wind rose plot for 24 hour period

The wind rose plot (figure 5) is overlaid on the storage tank of DAPFCL for the convenience of visualization.

Figure 6: Wind rose plot overlaid on the DAPFCL storage tank

The results of consequence predictions can vary to a significant extent based on input weather parameters like wind speed, direction, stability class etc. [12]. Table 2 shows the input parameters for the simulation.

Table 2: Input parameters for the simulation [13]

Parameters	Magnitude/Description
Ambient Temperature (°C)	28
Wind Speed (m/s)	2.1
Wind Direction	From South
Measurement Height (m)	4
Ground roughness	Urban/Forrest
Humidity (%)	89
Stability Class	F
Source Type	Direct
Amount of material released (MT)	368
Duration (Hour)	1
Release Type	Continuous

Threat zone from the case study of DAPFCL has been imported on our area of interest. The most dangerous red zone is 1100 ppm and it is about 7.1 km long. The second threat zone is 160 ppm and it is 10 km long. Concentration of third threat zone is 30 ppm. Figure 7 shows the simulation outcome. The footprint drawn here is based on the ground level concentration. Anhydrous ammonia gas is lighter than air. But at the initial stage of the release ammonia is heavier than air. It is interesting to note that the plume proceeds over the river water which certainly has a potential to absorb ammonia as ammonia has a high solubility in water. The simulation does not consider the effect of water body in its calculation.

From simulation we can see that the toxic footprint proceeds in a direction where there is least number of residential house and mostly open space resulting in low consequence. Hence, the simulation complies with the real scenario, i.e. 250 people were hospitalized with no fatality [4].

Figure 7: Toxic footprint for DAPFCL storage tank produced by ALOHA

3.2 Scenario B: KAFCO Storage Tank Explosion (Worst Case Scenario)

KAFCO has a production capacity of one thousand and five hundred metric ton ammonia per day and a total storage capacity of twenty thousand metric ton ammonia. For worst case scenario we consider the largest quantity of substance release, average wind speed, most frequent wind direction, maximum daily temperature and average humidity as input parameters [5]. Table 3 shows the input parameters for the simulation.

Table 3: Input Parameters for the simulation [13]

Parameters	Magnitude/Description
Ambient Temperature (°C)	39
Wind Speed (m/s)	1.5
Wind Direction	From SSW
Measurement Height (m)	4
Ground roughness	Urban/Forrest
Humidity (%)	70
Stability Class	F
Source Type	Direct
Amount of material released (MT)	20,000
Duration (Min.)	10
Release Type	Continuous

Threat zone for continuous dispersion created in the ALOHA for average atmospheric condition has been imported on the map in figure 8. The red zone is 1100 ppm and about 10 km long. For worst case scenario whole capacity (20000 MT) ammonia release has been considered. Simulation output is shown in Figure 8. From the simulation it is evident that if a similar kind of accident occurs in KAFCO, the aftermath will be dreadful as the toxic footprint passes through the residential area.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The consequence assessment involves determining the impact of an event in terms of its physical extent and severity (Lees, 1996). The physical extent of an accident scenario usually involves the calculation of the effect-distance (i.e. maximum distance with certain intensity) from the source within which people might get affected. The severity of an event is expressed as the level of harm to people such as injury or fatality [14]. In this research, physical effects of the reference scenarios were analyzed using ALOHA (Areal Locations of Hazardous Atmospheres).

Table 4: Maximum distance of red zone

Scenario ID	Maximum Distance of Red Zone (km)
A-DAPFCL	7.1
B-KAFCO	More than 10

ALOHA shows maximum 10 km distance for concentration footprint. However, the trend in release dispersion shows that the red zone could extend up to 20 km.

Figure 8: Threat zone for KAFCO storage tank produced by ALOHA

5 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study has attempted to show the effect of toxic release on Chittagong industrial area. For this purpose the industrial zoning of Chittagong district is combined with Vector GIS Boundary Layer map of classified lands of Chittagong. Next, the consequence analysis of ammonia release for two fertilizer factories i.e. DAPFCL and KAFCO was carried out for real incident and worst case scenario, respectively. From consequence analysis we can identify the areas that the toxic footprint will cover. There is a scope for using the outcomes of this study to develop risk-informed land use planning strategy to reduce the risk at the societal level.

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